

Supplementary Methods S1: Missing Data in Sea Turtle Population Monitoring: A Bayesian Statistical Framework Accounting for Incomplete Sampling

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Here we provide some details of the models used, with exemplar code for running a single site/season.

```
## load libraries
library(tidyverse)
library(magrittr)
library(nimble)
library(coda)
library(patchwork)
```

1 Data

The data are stored as a `csv` file in the file `turtles.csv`, with columns:

- `season` `<chr>`: a season indicator;
- `site` `<chr>`: a site indicator;
- `species` `<chr>`: a species indicator (`Leatherback` or `Olive Ridley`);
- `datestart` `<date>`: the start dates of the sampling periods;
- `dateend` `<date>`: the end dates of the sampling periods;
- `nests` `<dbl>`: the total number of clutches found during that sampling period;
- `refdate` `<date>`: the reference date for the start of the season for each data set.

We can load and examine this data set as:

```
turtles <- read_csv("turtles.csv")
turtles
```

```
## # A tibble: 13,056 x 7
##   season  site  species  datestart  dateend  nests  refdate
##   <chr>   <chr> <chr>    <date>    <date>  <dbl> <date>
## 1 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-10-27 2000-10-28 0 2000-09-01
## 2 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-10-28 2000-10-29 1 2000-09-01
## 3 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-10-29 2000-10-30 0 2000-09-01
## 4 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-10-31 2000-11-01 0 2000-09-01
## 5 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-11-01 2000-11-02 0 2000-09-01
## 6 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-11-02 2000-11-03 0 2000-09-01
## 7 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-11-03 2000-11-04 0 2000-09-01
## 8 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-11-04 2000-11-05 2 2000-09-01
## 9 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-11-05 2000-11-06 0 2000-09-01
## 10 2000-2001 Niandji Leatherback 2000-11-06 2000-11-07 2 2000-09-01
## # ... with 13,046 more rows
```

2 Models

Here we specify the Bayesian model used, and provide NIMBLE code to implement it. We also provide an exemplar example of how to fit to one data set and produce predictions, though we do not provide code to do this for all models here since there are a very large number of them, so we did all these calculations in parallel for the complete analysis. Full code for the complete analysis is available on request.

2.1 Model structure

The model has the mean number of new clutches in a period $(t - 1, t]$ as:

$$\mu_{(t-1):t} = \begin{cases} \alpha \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t-t_p+t_f}{s_1} \right)^2 \right] & \text{for } t < t_p - t_f, \\ \alpha & \text{for } t_p - t_f < t < t_p + t_f, \\ \alpha \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t-t_p-t_f}{s_2} \right)^2 \right] & \text{for } t > t_p + t_f \end{cases}$$

with the observed number of clutches in time period $(t - k, t]$ as:

$$Y_{(t-1):t} \sim \text{NB}(\mu_{(t-1):t}, \phi).$$

and depends on parameters $\alpha > 0$ (controlling the magnitude; the average number of new clutches around the peak), t_p (controlling the date of the peak nesting effort), t_f defining a region of constant nesting effort around the peak, and $s_1, s_2 > 0$ (controlling the rates of increase and decrease of the nesting effort around the peak; larger values corresponding to the nesting effort having slower rates of increase and decline respectively). The parameter $\phi > 0$ is a size parameter for the negative binomial distribution, such that as $\phi \rightarrow \infty$, the NB converges to a Poisson distribution. Suitable prior distributions are given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &\sim \text{Exp} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_m} \right), \\ s_1 &\sim \text{Exp}(s_r) \\ s_2 &\sim \text{Exp}(s_r), \\ t_p &\sim N \left(120, \sigma_{t_p}^2 \right), \\ t_f &\sim \text{Exp}(0.2), \\ \phi &\sim T[\text{InvG}(1, 0.1), 0, 50], \end{aligned}$$

with hyperparameters:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{t_p} &\sim U(0, 10), \\ s_r &\sim U(0.01, 10), \\ \alpha_m &\sim \text{Exp}(1).\end{aligned}$$

Here $\text{Exp}(\nu)$ denotes an exponential random variable with rate ν ; $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ denotes a normal distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2 ; $U(a, b)$ is a uniform distribution with bounds a and b ; $\text{InvG}(\theta, k)$ is an inverse-gamma distribution with shape parameter θ and rate parameter k ; and T (distribution, L, U) denotes a truncated distribution between L and U . We re-scaled time t , such that $t = 0$ corresponded to September 1st in any given year. We didn't find it necessary to explicitly bound t_p to be in the period $(0, 241)$, though this could be built into the prior distribution if required.

Note: we found that a (non-centred) re-parametrisation produced better mixing, in which we used priors:

$$t_p^* \sim N(0, 1),$$

and then set

$$t_p = 120 + \sigma_{t_p} t_p^*,$$

and this is reflected in the NIMBLE code below.

Firstly we must load in the `dSnbinomNim()` function, which is provided in the [Appendix](#) and must be read in before running the subsequent code. Then we can create a `nimbleFunction` object containing the mean function:

```
meanFnNim <- nimbleFunction(  
  run = function(t = double(0), alpha = double(0), s1 = double(0),  
                 s2 = double(0), tf = double(0), tp = double(0)) {  
    if(t < (tp - tf)) {  
      mu <- alpha * exp(-((t - tp + tf) / s1)^2)  
    } else {  
      if(t < (tp + tf)) {  
        mu <- alpha  
      } else {  
        mu <- alpha * exp(-((t - tp - tf) / s2)^2)  
      }  
    }  
    return(mu)  
    returnType(double(0))  
  }  
)
```

We have found that NIMBLE prefers all initial values to be explicitly specified, so we provide a function `model_inits()` in the [Appendix](#) to generate valid initial values. Again, this must be read in before specifying the model as:

```

## NIMBLE code for model
model_code <- nimbleCode({
  ## likelihood
  for(i in 1:N) {
    for(j in 1:nt[i]) {
      mu[i, j] <- meanFnNim(t[i, j], alpha, s1, s2, tf, tp)
    }
    Y[i] ~ dSnbinomNim(phi, mu[i, ], nt[i])
  }

  ## priors
  alpha_mn ~ dexp(1)
  alpha_rate <- 1 / alpha_mn
  alpha ~ dexp(alpha_rate)
  s_rate ~ dunif(0.01, 10)
  s1 ~ dexp(s_rate)
  s2 ~ dexp(s_rate)
  stp ~ dunif(0, 10)
  tp_ast ~ dnorm(0, sd = 1)
  tp <- 120 + tp_ast * stp
  tf ~ dexp(0.2)
  phi ~ T(dinvgamma(shape = 1, rate = 0.1), , 50)
})

```

As an illustration, we can fit the model to data from Niandji for leatherbacks in 2000–2001 as:

```

## extract data
turtles <- filter(turtles,
  season == "2000-2001",
  species == "Leatherback",
  site == "Niandji")

## convert to correct form for NIMBLE
model_data <- turtles %>%
  mutate(day = as.numeric(dateend - refdate)) %>%
  arrange(day) %$%
  list(t = day, Y = nests)
model_consts <- list(N = length(model_data$Y))
days <- model_data$t

## create sampling windows
sampWindow <- 7
tdiffs <- diff(c(0, days))
tdiffs[tdiffs > sampWindow] <- sampWindow
tdiffs <- map2(tdiffs, days, function(tdiff, t) (t - tdiff + 1):t)
t <- matrix(NA, length(days), sampWindow)
for(i in 1:length(tdiffs)) {
  t[i, 1:length(tdiffs[[i]])] <- tdiffs[[i]]
}

model_consts$t <- t
model_consts$nt <- map_int(tdiffs, length)
model_data$t <- NULL

```

```

## define the model
model <- nimbleModel(
  code = model_code,
  constants = model_consts,
  data = model_data,
  dimensions = list(mu = dim(model_consts$t))
)

## compile the model
cmodel <- compileNimble(model)

## set monitors
config <- configureMCMC(cmodel,
  monitors = c("alpha", "s1", "s2", "tf", "tp", "phi"), thin = 1)

## build the MCMC algorithm
built <- buildMCMC(config)
cbuilt <- compileNimble(built)

```

Now that the model is compiled, we run for 40,000 iterations removing the first 10,000 iterations as burn-in:

```

## sample initial values
inits <- list()
for(i in 1:2) {
  inits[[i]] <- model_inits(days, model_data$Y, meanFnNim, cmodel)
}

## run the model for multiple chains
model_fit <- runMCMC(cbuilt,
  niter = 40000,
  nburnin = 10000,
  nchains = 2,
  inits = inits,
  progressBar = TRUE,
  samplesAsCodaMCMC = TRUE,
  thin = 1)

```

```
## Running chain 1 ...
```

```
## Running chain 2 ...
```

```
## produce summary plots
plot(model_fit)
```



```
## calculate diagnostics
gelman.diag(model_fit)
```

```
## Potential scale reduction factors:
##
##      Point est. Upper C.I.
## alpha          1          1
## phi            1          1
## s1             1          1
## s2             1          1
## tf             1          1
## tp             1          1
##
## Multivariate psrf
##
## 1
```

Posterior mean estimates of the average nesting trajectory over time can be derived as:

```
## extract a smaller subset of samples for predictions
samples <- as.matrix(model_fit)
samples <- samples[sample.int(nrow(samples), 2000, replace = FALSE), ]

## set maxday for sampling
maxday <- 241
```

```

## predictions of mean at each day of the year
mean_lines <- samples %>%
  apply(1, function(x, t) {
    map_dbl(t, function(t, pars) {
      meanFnNim(t, pars[1], pars[3], pars[4], pars[5], pars[6])
    }, pars = x)
  }, t = 1:maxday) %>%
  t()

## extract posterior mean line
mean_fits <- apply(mean_lines, 2, mean)

```

In order to compare model predictions to the observed data, we note that on a given sampling day, the number of observed new clutches represents the cumulative number of new clutches made since the previous sampling date (up to a maximum of seven days previously). Therefore the fitted lines must accommodate any gaps in the sampling accordingly to make for a fair comparison.

```

## rearrange data
turtles <- mutate(turtles, day = as.integer(dateend - refdate))

## set minimum day for cumulating for assessing
## model fits
minday <- max(1, min(turtles$day) - 7)

## extract dates relating to known data points
known_dates <- select(turtles, day) %>%
  mutate(group = as.character(day)) %>%
  complete(day = 1:maxday) %>%
  filter(day >= minday) %>%
  fill(group, .direction = "up") %>%
  group_by(group) %>%
  nest() %>%
  mutate(n = map_int(data, nrow)) %>%
  mutate(data = map2(data, n, function(x, y, twindow) {
    if(y > twindow) {
      x <- mutate(x, n = 1:nrow(x)) %>%
        arrange(-n) %>%
        slice(1:twindow) %>%
        arrange(n) %>%
        select(-n)
    }
    x
  }, twindow = 7)) %>%
  select(-n) %>%
  unnest(cols = data) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  mutate(group = as.numeric(group)) %>%
  na.omit()

```

```

## extract mean at each observed time point
mean_preds <- known_dates %$%
  split(day, group) %>%
  map(function(x, y){
    y <- y[, x, drop = FALSE]
    apply(y, 1, sum)
  }, y = mean_lines) %>%
  reduce(cbind)

## individual scale predictions at each time point
ind_preds1 <- matrix(
  rbinom(1:prod(dim(mean_lines))),
  size = rep(samples[, "phi"], ncol(mean_lines)),
  mu = as.vector(mean_lines),
  nrow(mean_lines), ncol(mean_lines))

## individual scale predictions at each observed time point
ind_preds <- known_dates %$%
  split(day, group) %>%
  map(function(x, y){
    y <- y[, x, drop = FALSE]
    apply(y, 1, sum)
  }, y = ind_preds1) %>%
  reduce(cbind)

```

So `mean_preds` is a matrix of posterior samples for the average clutch frequency at each observed sampling date, and `ind_preds` is a matrix of posterior predictive samples for the number of clutches at each observed sampling date.

In addition, we also want to produce estimates for the *cumulative nesting effort* over time, which we can do easily by summing up the total number of clutches at each time point for each set of posterior samples:

```

## cumulative predictions at each observed time point
## reduced to summaries
cum_preds <- apply(ind_preds, 1, cumsum) %>%
  apply(1, function(x) {
    c(mean(x), quantile(x, probs = c(0.025, 0.975)))
  }) %>%
  t() %>%
  set_colnames(c("mean", "LCI", "UCI")) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  cbind(select(turtles, day, dateend, nests)) %>%
  replace_na(list(nests = 0)) %>%
  mutate(dateend = turtles$refdate[1] + day - 1) %>%
  mutate(nests = cumsum(nests))

```

Thus `cum_preds` is a data frame containing posterior predictive summaries for the cumulative number of clutches at each observed time point, plus the observed data.

Since sampling is incomplete, the model provides a tool that can extrapolate or predict to time periods where no sampling has occurred. After consulting with the field teams, we make the assumption that within each sampling window, all new clutches are found. Hence, in order to produce predictions for the number of clutches in each sampled season, it makes sense to condition the predictions from the model on the observed counts. In this case the total number of observed cases constitutes a lower bound on the total number of clutches at a given site in a given season. To produce these estimates:

```

## conditional cumulative predictions across whole season
## conditioned on observations being exact in time windows
cum_fullpred <- ind_preds1
cum_fullpred[, known_dates$day] <- 0
cum_fullpred[, turtles$day] <- matrix(rep(turtles$nest, each = nrow(cum_fullpred)),
                                     nrow = nrow(cum_fullpred))

cum_fullpred %<>%
  apply(1, cumsum) %>%
  apply(1, function(x) {
    c(mean(x), quantile(x, probs = c(0.025, 0.975)))
  }) %>%
  set_rownames(c("mean", "LCI", "UCI")) %>%
  t() %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(day = 1:maxday) %>%
  mutate(dateend = turtles$refdate[1] + day - 1)

```

The final stage is to summarise the `ind_preds` and `mean_preds` distributions, and wrangle them into a suitable format for plotting.

```

## reduce to summaries
ind_preds %<>%
  apply(2, function(x) {
    c(mean(x), quantile(x, probs = c(0.025, 0.975)))
  }) %>%
  set_rownames(c("mean", "LCI", "UCI")) %>%
  t() %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(day = turtles$day)

## reduce to summaries
mean_preds %<>%
  apply(2, function(x) {
    c(mean(x), quantile(x, probs = c(0.025, 0.975)))
  }) %>%
  set_rownames(c("mean", "LCI", "UCI")) %>%
  t() %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(day = turtles$day)

## save posterior mean line estimates as data frame for plotting
mean_fits <- data.frame(dateend = turtles$refdate[1] + 1:maxday, mn = mean_fits)

```

```

## merge non-cumulative predictions
preds <- inner_join(
  ind_preds,
  mean_preds,
  by = "day",
  suffix = c("_ind", "_mean")
) %>%
inner_join(select(turtles, day, dateend, nests), by = "day") %>%
select(-mean_mean) %>%
gather(key, value, -day, -dateend, -nests) %>%
separate(key, c("measure", "scale"), sep = "_") %>%
spread(measure, value)

```

To plot these we can do:

```

plots <- list(NULL)
p <- preds %>%
  mutate(scale = ifelse(scale == "ind", "Individual", "Mean"))
plots[[1]] <- ggplot(p, aes(x = dateend)) +
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = LCI, ymax = UCI, fill = scale), alpha = 0.5) +
  geom_point(aes(y = nests)) +
  geom_line(aes(y = mean), data = filter(p, scale == "ind")) +
  geom_line(aes(y = mn), data = mean_fits, linetype = "dashed", colour = "red") +
  ylab("Number of clutches") +
  xlab("Date") +
  labs(fill = "Pred. Level")
plots[[2]] <- ggplot(cum_preds, aes(x = dateend)) +
  geom_line(aes(y = mean)) +
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = LCI, ymax = UCI), alpha = 0.5) +
  geom_point(aes(y = nests)) +
  xlab("Date") +
  ylab("Cumulative number of clutches") +
  ylim(0, max(cum_preds$UCI, cum_fullpred$UCI))
plots[[3]] <- ggplot(cum_fullpred, aes(x = dateend)) +
  geom_line(aes(y = mean)) +
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin = LCI, ymax = UCI), alpha = 0.5) +
  xlab("Date") +
  ylab("Conditional cumulative number of clutches") +
  ylim(0, max(cum_preds$UCI, cum_fullpred$UCI))

## produce plots using patchwork
wrap_plots(plots, ncol = 3) +
  plot_annotation(title = "Niandji - 2000-2001 - Leatherback") +
  plot_layout(guides = "collect") &
  xlim(min(mean_fits$dateend), max(mean_fits$dateend)) &
  theme(
    text = element_text(size = 18),
    plot.title = element_text(size = 18),
    legend.text = element_text(size = 18),
    legend.position = "bottom"
  )

```

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or extract the final time point as an estimate e.g.

```
cum_fullpred[nrow(cum_fullpred), ]
```

```
## # A tibble: 1 x 5
##   mean  LCI  UCI  day dateend
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <int> <date>
## 1  197.  185  214  241 2001-04-29
```

Since we can generate full posterior distributions for the predicted counts, we can use these to sum across all sites within each season, in order to produce the estimates and bounds in **Figure 2** of the main manuscript.

3 Appendix

Source code for the `dSnbinomNim()` function is provided below and has been adapted from the `dSnbinom()` function provided in the `HelpersMG` package in R. You need to source both `dSnbinomNim` and `rSnbinomNim` in order to register a custom distribution with NIMBLE.

```
## adapted from the R code for dSnbinom() in the `HelpersMG` package
## by Marc Girondot distributed under the GPL (>=2) licence. Adapted
## by me (TJ McKinley), so any errors introduced are my fault.
## (I have also taken out some of the checks to be more
## efficient in the MCMC)

## probability density function
dSnbinomNim <- nimbleFunction(
  run = function(x = double(0), size = double(0), mu = double(1),
                nt = integer(0), log = integer(0, default = 0)) {
    returnType(double(0))

    if(nt < 1) {
      print("'nt' must be >= 1")
      return(NA)
    }
    if(nt > length(mu)) {
      print("'nt' must be less than the length of 'mu'")
      return(NA)
    }
    mu1 <- numeric(nt)
    for(i in 1:nt) mu1[i] <- mu[i]

    if(any(mu1 < 0) | size <= 0) {
      print("dSnbinomNim must have positive mu and size")
      return(NA)
    }
    if(x < 0) {
      print("dSnbinomNim must have x >= 0")
      return(NA)
    }
    if(all(mu1 == 0) & x > 0) {
      if(log) {
        return(-Inf)
      } else {
        return(0)
      }
    }
    niter <- 1000
    tol <- 0.0000001

    p <- size / (size + mu1)

    if(length(mu1) == 1) {
      return(dnbinom(x, size, p[1], log = log))
    } else {
      q <- 1 - p
      p1 <- max(p)
    }
  }
)
```

```

q1 <- 1 - p1

qp1 <- (q * p1) / (q1 * p)
R1 <- qp1
for(i in 1:length(R1)) {
  R1[i] <- R1[i]^(-size)
}
R <- sum(log(R1))

delta <- c(1, rep(NA, niter))
xi <- rep(NA, niter)

tqp1 <- 1 - ((q1 * p) / (q * p1))
tqp2 <- tqp1
xi[1] <- sum((size * tqp2))
delta[2] <- xi[1] * delta[1]
i <- 2
val <- 2 * tol
if(is.na(val) | is.nan(val)) return(NA)
while(val >= tol & i <= niter) {
  for(j in 1:length(tqp1)) {
    tqp2[j] <- tqp1[j]^i
  }
  xi[i] <- sum((size * tqp2) / i)
  delta[i + 1] <- sum(c(1:i) * xi[1:i] * delta[i + 1 - c(1:i)]) / i
  val <- abs(xi[i] - xi[i - 1])
  if(is.na(val) | is.nan(val)) return(NA)
  i <- i + 1
}
delta1 <- delta[1:i]
size1 <- length(mu1) * size + c(1:i) - 1
p11 <- rep(p1, i)
PrS <- sum(delta1 * dnbinom(x, size1, p11))
if(log) {
  return(R + log(PrS))
} else {
  return(exp(R) * PrS)
}
}
})

## function to produce random samples
rSnbinomNim <- nimbleFunction(
  run = function(n = integer(0), size = double(0), mu = double(1),
    nt = integer(0)) {
    returnType(integer(0))

    if(n != 1) print("rSnbinomNim only allows n = 1; using n = 1.")
    n <- 1

    if(nt < 1) {
      print("'nt' must be >= 1")
      return(NA)
    }
  }
)

```

```

if(nt > length(mu)) {
  print("'nt' must be less than the length of 'mu'")
  return(NA)
}
mu1 <- numeric(nt)
for(i in 1:nt) mu1[i] <- mu[i]

if(any(mu1 < 0) | size <= 0) {
  print("rSnbinoMim must have positive mu and size")
  return(NA)
}
if(all(mu1 == 0)) {
  return(0)
}

p <- size / (size + mu1)

S <- 0
for(i in 1:nt) {
  S <- S + rnbinoM(1, p[i], size)
}
return(S)
})

```

The `model_inits()` function code is below:

```

## function to generate initial values
model_inits <- function(t, y, meanFn, model, sampWindow = 7) {
  valid <- 0
  while(valid == 0) {
    ## sample initial values from the priors
    alpha_mn <- rexp(1, 1)
    alpha_rate <- 1 / alpha_mn
    alpha <- rexp(1, alpha_rate)
    s_rate <- runif(1, 0.01, 10)
    s1 <- rexp(1, s_rate)
    s2 <- s1
    tp_ast <- rnorm(1, 0, 1)
    stp <- runif(1, 0, 10)
    tp <- 120 + tp_ast * stp
    tf <- rexp(1, 0.2)
    phi <- 51
    while(phi > 50) phi <- rexp(1, 1)
    tdiffs <- diff(c(0, t))
    tdiffs[tdiffs > sampWindow] <- sampWindow
    tdiffs <- map2(tdiffs, t, function(tdiff, t) (t - tdiff + 1):t)
    mu <- matrix(NA, length(t), sampWindow)
    for(i in 1:length(tdiffs)) {
      for(j in 1:length(tdiffs[[i]])) {
        mu[i, j] <- meanFn(tdiffs[[i]][j], alpha, s1, s2, tf, tp)
      }
    }
    mu[is.na(mu)] <- 0
  }
}

```

```
inits <- list(  
  alpha_mn = alpha_mn,  
  alpha_rate = alpha_rate,  
  alpha = alpha,  
  s_rate = s_rate,  
  s1 = s1,  
  s2 = s2,  
  stp = stp,  
  tp_ast = tp_ast,  
  tp = tp,  
  tf = tf,  
  phi = phi,  
  mu = mu  
)  
## check validity of initial values  
model$setInits(inits)  
valid <- ifelse(!is.finite(model$calculate()), 0, 1)  
}  
inits  
}
```